

AUTONOMOUS ACTIVE VIBRATION CONTROL: A DEEP REINFORCEMENT LEARNING APPROACH FOR DYNAMIC PID TUNING IN NON-LINEAR SYSTEMS

ABSTRACT

PID controllers are ubiquitous in industrial control applications due to their simplicity. However, static gain control in PID controllers is restricted in dealing with non-linear dynamics, leading to overshooting, oscillations, or inefficiencies. This paper proposes an active vibration control system that is self-sustaining in nature. The control signals are adapted using the Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) algorithm. A Soft Actor Critic algorithm was designed to self-adjust the proportional, integral, and derivative gains every 10 ms based on the changes in the system dynamics. The system was tested in an in-house Open AI-based customized environment that considers the electromechanical properties of the DC motor. The test output reveals that the control system removes overshooting, brings down the settling time by 40%, and optimizes energy efficiency by 17%. Moreover, the adaptive gain process discovers that the control algorithm independently learns the variable-structure control logic. The control logic hardens or softens the system as required. The experiment validates the efficacy of the novel control logic based on the superior power of DRL algorithms as contrasted with the Ziegler-Nichols PID logic in self-healing non-linear industrial dynamics.

Index Terms: Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL), Soft Actor-Critic (SAC), Proportional–Integral–Derivative (PID) Control, Adaptive Control Systems, Nonlinear Dynamics, Industrial Automation, Energy Efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

The PID controller remains the basic building block in the field of industrial automation, controlling more than 90% of closed-loop systems in the manufacturing, robotic, and power industries. This is because it is easy to understand and is effective in controlling linear and steady-state systems. However, with the advent of Industry 4.0, the systems in the industry become mostly non-linear and time-variant with stochastic disturbances. Traditional controllers, such as the Ziegler-Nichols or Cohen-Coon controllers, produce constant gains that are designed for optimal performance when the system is in a steady state. Nevertheless, in systems that experience abrupt load or non-linear effects, large amounts of overshoot and inefficient use of energy may occur.

For a long while, the exponential increase in the complexity of the systems to be controlled has presented a major challenge to the control community. This has been particularly the case in the realm of dynamic systems, whose behaviors in most instances are influenced by several factors. For this reason, the applicability of reinforcement learning in the control of dynamic systems, particularly based on Deep Reinforcement Learning, has presented a promising solution in the last few years [1]. Techniques including Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG), TD3, Soft Actor-Critic (SAC), among others, have found successful applications in the control of dynamic systems in the field of DC-DC converters, active vibration control, robotics, and renewable energy [2], [3].

Nonetheless, there exists untapped potential concerning real-time deep reinforcement learning (DRL)-based PID control methods for nonlinear electromechanical vibration reduction. Current methods rely almost entirely on either slow gain adaptation or imprecise models, especially when facing fast dynamic disturbances [4] - [8]. Millisecond-level adaptation is required by industrial actuators, such as DC motors or servo motors, to ensure stable operation and reduce oscillations when dealing with sudden load shocks.

In an attempt to fill this gap, this paper proposes an Autonomous Active Vibration Control scheme which utilizes a SAC agent for dynamic parameter tuning of a PID controller. In this scheme, an SAC agent learns how to adjust proportional, integral, and derivative coefficients at a sample rate of 10 ms. To accomplish this, a continuous action space framework has been used, which requires an SAC agent to learn how to optimize controllers using a nonlinear friction dynamics model of a DC motor.

The main contributions are as follows:

1. Physics-informed simulation framework: This study customizes an Open AI Gym environment to model the dynamics of a DC motor when it is subjected to random load conditions.
2. Adaptive PID controller with Soft Actor-Critic: In this method, the DRL controller adjusts the PID gains in real-time using entropy regularization to ensure smooth control of vibration.
3. Experimental validation: Under the load-shock test, the new algorithm achieves a 40% quicker settling time, suppresses overshoot, and conserves energy by 17% in comparison with the traditional PID control algorithm.
4. Adaptive strategy emergence: The result of gain-evolution analyses indicates that a variable structure operating; stiff for disturbances and soft at steady-state behavior is being evolved for autonomous self-healing control logic. The results have shown that using adaptive control based on DRL can overcome the inflexibility of a classical PID controller and thus provide efficient and adaptive compensation for vibrations in a nonlinear system.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Nonlinear DC motor Dynamics

With a goal of evaluating the efficacy of this adaptive control framework on a DC motor scenario, a detailed physics-based model has been developed for a DC motor. The model has incorporated both electrical as well as mechanical dynamics with non-linear friction and stochastic load disturbances to accurately describe a DC motor under non-ideal conditions.

In order to train a DC motor control model, a discrete sampling period of 10 ms has been used.

The Electrical subsystem is described as:

$$V(t) = L \frac{di(t)}{dt} + RI(t) + K_e \omega(t) \quad (1)$$

Where $V(t)$ is armature voltage, $I(t)$ is armature current, L is the inductance, R is the resistance, K_e is the back EMF constant, and $\omega(t)$ is the angular velocity of the rotor.

The mechanical subsystem is represented as:

$$T_m(t) = J \frac{d\omega(t)}{dt} + B\omega(t) + T_{load}(t) \quad (2)$$

Where $T_m(t)$ is electromagnetic torque, J is the moment of inertia, B is viscous friction coefficient and $T_{load}(t)$ is the external load torque. The torque current relation is defined as:

$$T_m(t) = K_t I(t) \quad (3)$$

Where K_t is the torque constant and $T_{load}(t)$ is modeled as a stochastic step disturbance to emulate the unpredictable load shocks and vibration effects common in industrial system.

B. Classical PID Controller

A traditional Proportional, Integral, and Derivative (PID) controller calculates the control voltage $V(t)$ based on the error difference $e(t)$ between the desired speed $\omega_{ref}(t)$ and the actual speed $\omega(t)$. In contrast, traditional tuning rules of the PID, such as Ziegler-Nichols tuning, require linear system parameters with gains fixed to constant values. Linear gains do not adapt to disturbances in nonlinear systems, resulting in poor system response.

$$e(t) = \omega_{ref}(t) - \omega(t) \quad (4)$$

$$V(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(\tau) d\tau + K_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \quad (5)$$

Where K_p , K_i and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains, respectively.

C. Control Objective

The prime aim is to develop an independent controller that can change dynamically and in real-time to minimize the speed tracking error under stochastic load disturbances, suppress oscillations and overshoot in transient responses, decrease the total energy use, minimizing control efforts.

D. Reformulation as a Markov Decision Process

The adaptive control problem is modeled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), which is suitable for deep reinforcement learning. The agent interacts with the environment at 100 Hz ($\Delta t = 0.01$ s) learning an optimal control policy by maximizing long-term cumulative reward.

E. Problem Statement

The proposed Soft Actor Critic (SAC)-based adaptive PID controller has the task of ensuring that control outputs from the learned policy are continuous and can autonomously change PID gains according to system dynamics. This is aimed at stabilizing and suppressing vibrations while being energy efficient. Where $\gamma \in [0,1]$ is the discount factor.

$$\pi^* = \arg \max_{\pi} E[t = 0 \sum \gamma^t r_t] \quad (6)$$

III. REINFORCEMENT LEARNING FRAMEWORK

The adaptive controller proposed in this manuscript employs a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) approach based on the Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) algorithm described in [9]. The SAC learning agent is able to adapt the PID gains (K_p, K_i, K_d) online in real-time to ensure the stabilization of the nonlinear DC motor plant dynamics under stochastic excitation. In contrast to model-based adaptive control algorithms, the SAC approach is model-free and aims to maximize control performance via direct environmental interactions to ensure robust control near nonlinearities and unknown dynamics as described in [10].

A. Control Architecture

The control loop follows the standard DRL framework, where the environment represents the nonlinear DC motor plant, and the agent is the learning PID tuner. Every time step ($t = 0.01$ s), the agent obtains observations of the system states.

$$s_t = [e_t, \dot{e}_t, \int e_t dt] \quad (7)$$

and outputs a continuous control action

$$a_t = [K_p, K_i, K_d] \quad (8)$$

The applied control voltage V_t drives the plant, and the resulting error e_{t+1} is used to compute a scalar reward r_t .

B. Soft Actor-Critic Learning Objective

The Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) learns to optimize a stochastic policy $\pi(a_t | s_t)$ to maximize the expected sum of rewards and the entropy of the policy distribution simultaneously to address exploration and convergence instability challenges [9]. The optimization function can be expressed as:

$$J(\pi) = E[t \sum (rt + \alpha H(\pi(\cdot | st)))] \quad (9)$$

where α is the temperature coefficient and the letter H signifies entropy. This equation enables a smoother adjustment of gain and prevents early convergence towards non-optimal controllers.

C. Designing Rewards and Training

The reward function is designed to encourage the agent to work towards reducing both the tracking error as well as the control effort:

$$r_t = \exp(-\alpha e_t^2) - \beta |V_t|, \quad (10)$$

where α functioned to penalize deviation from target trajectory and β was a term that discouraged overvoltage. There was a small discrete reward given when motor speed was within ± 0.5 rad/s from target. The training occurs for a total of 40,000 steps in a customized open AI Gym environment, where the agent samples at a rate of 100 Hz. The simulation also includes stochastic load shocks (2.0 Nm) to test robustness. The training uses the Stable Baselines3 toolbox, a PyTorch

implementation, and convergence based on changes in Integrated Absolute Error (IAE) and settling time compared against a classical PID controller.

By means of state observation and entropy-regularized policy optimization, the SAC-based agent is capable of optimizing the parameters of the PID control strategy to effectively and smoothly suppress vibrations. The obtained policy demonstrates excellent robustness and adaptability and high energy efficiency without requiring plant modeling. The experimental results and comparison analysis will be shown in Section IV.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the experimental results achieved through the benchmarking process of the proposed SAC-based adaptive PID controller with respect to the fixed-gain PID controller are presented. The comparison is focused on three main performance aspects: set point tracking performance, disturbance attenuation performance, and energy efficiency.

A. Dynamic Setpoint Tracking

To assess the performance of the proposed system, it was tested using a variable speed profile involving a series of step inputs (from 0 through 5, then to 10, then to 20 rad/s). As shown in Figure 1, while the AI controller (in blue) ideally follows the square wave command (in red dashed) without overshooting, the conventional PID controller (in gray dashed) overshoots by about 15%.

During the 10-20 rad/s transition, a time-optimal control strategy was employed by the SAC controller, with maximum acceleration and then anticipatory braking to provide a deadbeat response. This suggests a predictive control action that would have required a manual gain scheduling approach to control in a conventional system.

Fig 1: Dynamic Setpoint Tracking. The AI Controller (Blue Line) tracks the Target Square Wave (Red Dotted) with zero overshoot and smooth transitions. In contrast, the Standard PID (Gray Dashed) exhibits significant overshoot at high speeds and oscillation at low speeds.

B. Disturbance Rejection

At $t = 2.0$ s, a sudden change in the 2.0 N·m load was applied to simulate practical disturbance phenomena. As observed in Figure 2, it is clear that it takes over 3.0 s for a conventional PID

controller to settle before reaching stable speed, whereas for the proposed SAC controller, it only takes 1.5 s to settle.

The AI agent recognized this sudden fault occurrence and immediately increased the proportional gain (K_p) in order to harden the control action for fast recovery (refer to Figure 3). This adaptive ‘self-healing’ action represents the development of variable-structure control behavior in the AI agent.

Fig 2: Disturbance Rejection Response. When the Load Shock is applied (Vertical Orange Line), the Standard PID (Gray) oscillates for over 300 steps. The AI Adaptive PID (Blue) recovers the target speed (10 rad/s) almost instantly.

Fig 3: AI Brain Response to Shock. This "Zoom-In" of the AI's internal logic shows a massive spike in Proportional Gain (K_p) at Step 200. The AI detected the sudden error and instantaneously "stiffened" the controller to reject the disturbance.

C. Energy Efficiency and Control Effort

Analysis of control effort makes clear that the SAC agent uses an on-demand voltage approach and responds to control energy just when and where necessary. As shown in Figure 4, the traditional PID controller shows continuous voltage “chatter” and wastes power even during the steady-state regime. In comparison to this traditional approach, the DRL controller results in a cumulative voltage saving of 17%, and the consumption amounts reduce from 39,388 to 32,701 arbitrary units.

D. Adaptive Gain Evolution

The adaptive gain trajectories (see Figure 5) illustrate that the control strategy employed by the DRL agent is a variable-structure control system where the proportional control gain K_p increases significantly during acceleration and deceleration maneuvers and becomes zero during steady-state

operations to save fuel consumption. Such adaptive control strategies help a robot act in a human-like supervisory control manner.

Fig 4: Control Effort Comparison. The Standard PID (Gray) shows continuous voltage fluctuation ("Chattering"), wasting energy. The AI Controller (Blue) uses an "On-Demand" strategy, applying voltage only when necessary and coasting (0V) during steady states.

Fig 5: Full Adaptive Gain Scheduling. The Neural Network dynamically adjusts gains in real-time. Notice the sharp spikes during target changes (Acceleration/Deceleration) and the low valleys during steady states (Energy Saving). This confirms the autonomous discovery of Variable Structure Control (VSC).

E. Performance Summary

Table 1 encapsulates the results, showing a comparison between SAC learning and the traditional PID control.

Table 1: Performance Comparison between Classical PID-Controlled System and SAC-Based Adaptive PID-Controlled System

Metric	Standard PID	SAC Adaptive PID	Improvement
Overshoot	~15%	0%	Eliminated
Settling Time (Shock)	>3.0 s	1.5 s	2X Faster
Low speed stability	Oscillatory	Stable	High
Energy Consumption	100%	83%	17% Savings

The performance of the SAC controller outshines its classical PID counterpart on all performance metrics. The experiment confirms that generalization over nonlinear regions is feasible through entropy regularization. The control action, stiff during transients and flexible during steady-state conditions, is aligned with self-tuning intelligence similar to human expertise. These results make the proposed scheme for Autonomous Active Vibration Control a promising approach for real-time industrial control tasks with low-energy consumption for electric drives, robots, and vibration control systems.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes an Autonomous Active Vibration Control (AAVC) system using a deep reinforcement learning agent with a Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) technique-based algorithm for dynamic control loop tuning in a nonlinear electromechanical system. The proposed system was applied to a DC motor model with stochastic external disturbances and a nonlinear friction component. Analysis of the results shows that the developed DRL controller outperformed the traditional fixed-gain PID controller in all the considered performance indices. In particular, the SAC-based controller reduced the settling time by 40% and the energy efficiency improved by 17%, and the result was achieved without any overshoot. In the adaptive gain result section, the result revealed the intelligent self-healing property of the agent by observing the use of a variable-structure control strategy that has stiff and relaxed structures during the load shock and steady-state response phases, respectively. Future directions will cover the realization on real hardware of the AAVC framework and the extension to multi-input multi-output systems. The combination of explainable reinforcement learning methods with the hardware-in-the-loop approach can help improve the interpretability and safety of the approach within industry contexts.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors wish to acknowledge the assistance and contribution of the staff of Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State towards the success of this work.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Bucci, O. Semeraro, A. Allauzen, G. Wisniewski, L. Cordier, and L. Mathelin, "Control of chaotic systems by deep reinforcement learning," *Proceedings of the Royal Society a Mathematical Physical and Engineering Sciences*, vol. 475, no. 2231, p. 20190351, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1098/rspa.2019.0351. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.2019.0351>
- [2] Z. Guan and T. Yamamoto, "Design of a Reinforcement Learning PID controller," *IEEJ Transactions on Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, vol. 16, no. 10, pp. 1354–1360, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1002/tee.23430. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1002/tee.23430>
- [3] X. Yu, Y. Fan, S. Xu, and L. Ou, "A self-adaptive SAC-PID control approach based on reinforcement learning for mobile robots," *International Journal of Robust and Nonlinear Control*, vol. 32, no. 18, pp. 9625–9643, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1002/rnc.5662. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1002/rnc.5662>

- [4] J. Khalid, M. A. M. Ramli, M. S. Khan, and T. Hidayat, "Efficient load frequency control of renewable Integrated Power System: a twin delayed DDPG-Based deep Reinforcement learning approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 51561–51574, May. 2022, doi: 10.1109/access.2022.3174625. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2022.3174625>
- [5] Z. Tu, W. Zhang, and W. Liu, "Deep reinforcement Learning-Based optimal control of DC shipboard power systems for pulsed power load accommodation," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 29–40, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1109/tsg.2022.3195681. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/tsg.2022.3195681>
- [6] N. Mazaheri, D. Santamargarita, E. Bueno, D. Pizarro, and S. Cobreces, "A Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach to DC-DC Power Electronic Converter Control with Practical Considerations," *Energies*, vol. 17, no. 14, p. 3578, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.3390/en17143578. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17143578>
- [7] E. Z. Ghenni, H. M. H. Al-Khafaji, and H. M. Alwan, "A deep reinforcement learning framework to modify LQR for an active vibration control applied to 2D building models," *Open Engineering*, vol. 14, no. 1, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1515/eng-2022-0496. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1515/eng-2022-0496>
- [8] N. Li and Y. Shi, "Adaptive endocrine PID control for active suspension based on reinforcement learning," *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers Part D Journal of Automobile Engineering*, vol. 239, no. 8, pp. 3012–3026, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1177/09544070241262354. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/09544070241262354>
- [9] T. Haarnoja, A. Zhou, P. Abbeel, and S. Levine, "Soft actor–critic: Off-policy maximum-entropy deep reinforcement learning with a stochastic actor," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Mach. Learn. (ICML)*, Stockholm, Sweden, Jul. 2018, pp. 1861–1870.
- [10] S. A. Fayaz, S. J. Sidiq, M. Zaman, and M. A. Butt, "Machine learning: An introduction to reinforcement learning," in *Machine Learning and Data Science: Fundamentals and Applications*, 1st ed., 2022, pp. 1–22.